

Effects of Gibberellic Acid and Kinetin Treatments on *In vitro* Seedling Development, Total Phenolic Substance and Flavonoid Contents in Arugula

Ayşenur Ece ÇİÇEK¹, Abdulsalam REDHWAN^{2*}, Arda ACEMİ³, Fazıl ÖZEN⁴

¹ Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Hacettepe University, Ankara, 06001, Türkiye, ORCID: 0009-0005-7757-2327

² Department of Biology, Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, 41001, Türkiye, ORCID: 0000-0002-5326-5390

³ Department of Biology, Faculty of Arts and Sciences, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, 41001, Türkiye, ORCID: 0000-0003-0270-8507

⁴ Department of Biology, Faculty of Arts and Sciences, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, 41001, Türkiye, ORCID: 0000-0001-9293-908X

Article Info	Abstract
Oral Presentation	<p>The concentration-dependent effects of gibberellic acid (GA₃) and kinetin (KIN) on <i>in vitro</i> seed germination, organ development, and phenolic substance contents in arugula (<i>Eruca vesicaria</i> subsp. <i>sativa</i>) were investigated. The seed germination ratio and leaf production increased to 100% and 3.93 leaves, respectively, after GA₃ treatment at 0.25 mg L⁻¹. GA₃ at 0.25 mg L⁻¹ treatment also resulted in more elongated roots (4.03 cm) than the other treatments. However, the stimulative effect of GA₃ on root elongation was not recorded in root production. The highest root number (1.93 roots) was recorded from the control seedlings, and KIN treatments resulted in a concentration-dependent decrease in the parameter. Hypocotyl elongation was triggered after 0.25 mg L⁻¹ GA₃ treatment. Total phenolic substance (TPC) and flavonoid content (TFC) were estimated from methanolic extracts obtained through ultrasonic extraction and expressed as gallic acid (GA) and quercetin (Q) equivalents (E), respectively. A slight increase in the TPC to 11.57 mg GAE g⁻¹ DW was found after KIN treatment at 0.25 mg L⁻¹ compared to the control (10.35 mg GAE g⁻¹ DW). A similar trend was also recorded in TFCs. KIN treatments at 0.25 and 1.0 mg L⁻¹ increased the content (7.42 and 7.40 mg QE g⁻¹ DW, respectively) compared to the control (6.43 mg QE g⁻¹ DW). The results suggested that GA₃ and KIN treatments at 0.25 mg L⁻¹ can enhance arugula's growth parameters and phenolic substance content, respectively.</p>
Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14398224	
Keywords	

Eruca vesicaria
phenolic compounds
plant growth regulators
plant tissue culture

1. Introduction

Plants are essential natural resources for humans not only as food but also because of the medical benefits resulting from their secondary metabolites. Thus, plant research is important for scientific areas such as biotechnology and pharmacology [1]. Arugula (*Eruca vesicaria* subsp. *sativa* (Mill.) Thell.) is a leafy plant species belonging to the Brassicaceae family, known for its edible and medicinal properties. In addition, it is commonly utilised in traditional medicine as well as a source of nutrients. Arugula attracts attention with the nutritional benefits of its leaves and its positive effects on health [2]. *In vitro* techniques offer an effective way to produce plant products under controlled conditions. These culture methods facilitate rapid production and increase the efficiency of producing pharmaceutically important compounds [3]. Studies involving *in vitro* cultures are crucial for the sustainable production of plant species for various purposes ranging from food sources to raw materials with pharmaceutical

significance [4]. Plant tissue culture is an effective method to create *in vitro* environments for plant research. These techniques significantly increase the production of important phenolic compounds and flavonoids in plant species known for their health benefits. By promoting the sustainable production of compounds with high medicinal value, this approach contributes to both scientific research and health practices [5]. Research on phenolic and flavonoid compounds indicates that consuming leafy vegetables high in these substances is associated with a reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases, cancer, diabetes, and neurodegenerative disorders. Edible leafy plants are vital food sources for communities and are abundant in phytochemicals and antioxidants [6]. In this context, the potential concentration-dependent (0.25, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg L⁻¹) effects of plant growth regulators, namely gibberellic acid (GA₃) and kinetin (KIN) on seed germination, organ development and phenolic substance contents in arugula were investigated in an *in vitro* culture.

* Corresponding Author: abdulesalamredhwan@gmail.com

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Plant Material and Disinfection Method

Certified seeds of *Eruca vesicaria* subsp. *sativa* (Mill.) Thell. (arugula) obtained from a producer were used as plant material. For proper surface sterilization of plant material, seeds were disinfected with a solution consisting of 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and a few drops of Tween-20 for 12 min. Then, the seeds were rinsed with dH₂O at least 3 times and sown in culture media.

2.2. Medium Preparation

Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium [7], fortified with GA₃ and KIN concentrations at 0.25, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 mg L⁻¹ was used for the cultures. The medium was supplemented with 30 g L⁻¹ sucrose and solidified with 7 g L⁻¹ plant agar. The pH was adjusted to 5.7-5.8. Plant Preservative Mixture™ was added into medium at 1.0 mL L⁻¹ to eliminate contaminations during culture initiation. After medium sterilization in an autoclave for 20 min, thirty mL of the medium prepared was dispensed into each sterile Magenta GA-7 culture vessel.

2.3. Culture Conditions

Cultures were incubated at 23 ± 2°C under 60 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ photosynthetic photon flux density in a 16/8-hour light/dark period for 30 days. The morphometric parameters measured in the study were germination rate (%), leaf and root number and lengths and hypocotyl length. Fifteen seeds were sown per treatment, and each experiment was repeated thrice.

2.4. Preparation of The Extracts

Total phenol and flavonoid contents were determined using the extracts from *in vitro* leaves. Leaf samples were harvested from each treatment group, and the extracts were prepared according to the method described by Kiran Acemi et al. [8]. The harvested leaves were dried in an oven for 24 h at 60°C. The dry leaves were then powdered, and 50 mg of the sample was extracted in 1 mL of 80% methanol using an ultrasonic bath for 60 min at 55°C. The resulting solutions were then centrifuged at 4400 ×g for 10 min. The supernatants were collected and used in the experiments.

2.5. Determination of Total Phenolic Content

The method of Singleton et al. [9] was followed to determine the leaf phenolic substance content using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. The sample solution (500 μL), Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (250 μL) and H₂O (3 mL) were taken into

the same tube and stirred for 1 min. At the end of the incubation, 0.75 mL of 20% (w:v) Na₂CO₃ was added to the solution and vortexed for 30 s. The final volume was completed to 5 mL with H₂O. The solution's absorbance value at 750 nm was recorded after an incubation period of 30 min at room temperature. The phenolic content was calculated and compared with a calibration curve prepared using gallic acid at different concentrations (0.1-0.5 mg mL⁻¹, R² = 0.99) for quantification. The results were expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalent per gram leaf dry weight (mg GAE g⁻¹ DW).

2.6. Determination of Total Flavonoid Content

The method of Dewanto et al. [10] was used to estimate the total flavonoid content of the leaves. The sample solution (500 μL) was mixed with 75 μL of 5% (w:v) NaNO₂ and kept for 5 min at room temperature. Then, 150 μL of 10% (w:v) AlCl₃·6H₂O was added to the solution, and the solution was again kept for 5 min at room temperature. Finally, the solution was mixed with 0.5 mL of 1 M NaOH. After vortexing the final solution its final volume was completed to 2.5 mL with H₂O. The absorbance was recorded at 405 nm. The results were compared with a calibration curve prepared using quercetin at different concentrations (0.2-1.0 mg mL⁻¹, R² = 0.99). The results were expressed as mg quercetin equivalent per gram leaf dry matter (mg QE g⁻¹ DW).

2.7. Statistical Analysis

The data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation. The differences between the means were compared using Duncan's multiple range test at a significance level of *p* < 0.05. Statistical analysis was conducted through IBM SPSS Statistics software (ver. 22).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Seed germination and organ development

Plant development can be influenced by adding plant growth regulators (PGRs) to the nutrient medium at specific growth stages. Even in very low amounts, PGRs can significantly impact plant growth and development [11]. In this study, the presence of PGRs in the medium enhanced the germination of arugula seeds, especially at low GA₃ concentrations, reaching a 100.0% germination rate. The general appearance of the seedlings is given in Figure 1A. Similarly, a study conducted by Cüce and Muslu, found that the germination percentage of *E. sativa* seeds reached 90% in MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mg L⁻¹ 6-BA [12]. However, in the same study, the germination rate of the control medium decreased significantly to 76.67%. In our study, the germination rate was 86.67 ± 11.55% in the control

group. Banjac et al. reported a germination rate of about 95% for *E. sativa* seeds grown on a PGR-free MS medium [13]. The GA₃ treatment may be particularly effective in promoting seed germination by alleviating primary dormancy [14], which may explain the high germination rate in our study. These results indicate that low concentrations of GA₃ can significantly increase germination rates. Conversely, the other treatments of GA₃ and KIN at varying concentrations unexpectedly decreased the germination rate. KIN treatments at 0.25 and 0.5 mg L⁻¹ and GA₃ treatment at 0.5 mg L⁻¹ resulted in low germination percentages ($60.0 \pm 0.0\%$) and gave statistically similar results (Figure 1B). Leaf production increased in the presence of GA₃ at 0.25 mg L⁻¹ in the culture medium 3.93 ± 0.42 leaves per plant, while other applications gave leaf numbers similar to or lower than the control (3.07 ± 0.70) leaves per plant (Figure 1C). These results indicate that the effects of PGR treatments on germination rates and leaf production can vary based on both the concentration and the type of PGRs used.

Hypocotyl elongation is a significant developmental parameter for plants, enabling them to emerge from the soil surface. Many external variables influence the length of hypocotyl [15]. In this study, it was found that the 0.25 mg L⁻¹ GA₃ treatment promoted hypocotyl elongation (1.07 ± 0.14 cm). However, elongation was significantly reduced in all other treatments except for the control (0.91 ± 0.02 cm) and KIN treatment at 0.5 mg L⁻¹ concentration (0.89 ± 0.09 cm). These groups gave statistically similar results (Figure 1D). Cüce and Muslu, reported that the maximum average hypocotyl length in *E. sativa* was 29.80 ± 2.22 mm (2.80 cm) in MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mg L⁻¹ BAP and 15.72 ± 1.33 mm (1.57 cm) in the control [12]. Thus, low

concentrations of GA₃ can also be employed to increase hypocotyl length in arugula.

The rhizogenic response of arugula plants varied significantly depending on the PGRs used in the culture medium. The control group exhibited the highest average number of roots per plant (1.93 ± 0.23). Similarly, GA₃ treatment at 0.25 mg L⁻¹ showed statistically the same result and produced (1.67 ± 0.31) roots. KIN treatments significantly decreased the root production in a concentration-dependent way (Figure 1E). These findings suggest that KIN treatments can lead to varying root development, and specifically, high concentrations may negatively affect the rhizogenic responses in arugula plants. Roots elongation is important for plants to reach minerals and nutrients from the soil. In this study, it was observed that the most significant increase in organ development in arugula was observed in root elongation. In particular, 0.25 mg L⁻¹ GA₃ treatment significantly increased root elongation, resulting in roots with an average length of 4.03 ± 0.78 cm. In KIN treatments, significant differences were found between different concentrations. KIN treatment at 0.25 mg L⁻¹ gave a root length (2.41 ± 0.29 cm) close to the control (2.19 ± 0.38 cm) compared to the other treatments, whereas KIN treatment at 2.0 mg L⁻¹ significantly reduced root length and produced the shortest roots with an average of 0.29 ± 0.04 cm (Figure 1F). In *Arabidopsis*, cytokinins are found to reduce cell elongation, which results in the limitation of root elongation [16]. However, although the stimulatory effect of GA₃ on root elongation was observed, this increase did not correspond to an increase in root number. Li et al., stated that GA₃ can involve in auxin-mediated primary root elongation by modulating auxin signalling and transport [17].

Figure 1. General appearance of *in vitro* grown *Eruca vesicaria* subsp. *sativa* seeds on MS medium (A), and effects of GA₃ and KIN treatments on seed germination ratio (B), leaf production (C), hypocotyl length (D), root number (E) and length (F). The bars show standard deviations of mean values. Superscript letters indicate statistical differences between means according to Duncan's multiple range test ($p < 0.05$). Scale bar corresponds to 1 cm.

Total Phenolic substance and Flavonoid content

Phenolic compounds (PCs) are phytochemicals commonly found in various plant tissues, including fruits and vegetables [18]. Additionally, the aerial parts of plants are valuable for their medicinal properties and are rich in biologically active compounds, such as iridoids, phenolic acids, flavonoids, and saponins [19]. In this study, the treatment of 0.25 mg L⁻¹ KIN led to a slight increase in total phenolic content (TPC), reaching 11.57 ± 0.03 mg GAE g⁻¹ DW compared to the control group (10.35 ± 0.08 mg GAE g⁻¹ DW). In contrast, other PGR treatments resulted in statistically similar or lower TPC levels (Figure 2A). This suggests that low concentrations of KIN may promote the synthesis of phenolic compounds. Zappia et al., investigated the effects of dark and light conditions on TPC and in arugula. They reported that the TPC values ranged from 7.81 to 12.09 mg GAE g⁻¹ FW under dark conditions and from 7.75 to 12.09 mg GAE g⁻¹ FW under light conditions [20].

Additionally, other studies reported varying TPC values in arugula. For instance, Bouacida et al. [21] recorded approximately 22.50 mg GAE g⁻¹ extract in freeze-dried samples, while Tiveron et al. [22] found a TPC value of 11 mg GAE g⁻¹ DW. A similar content was observed by Mazzucotelli et al. [23], reporting 10.3 mg GAE g⁻¹ FW. However, a notably lower TPC of 4.63 mg GAE g⁻¹ extract was reported by Sihem et al. [24]. The diversity in TPCs demonstrates the impact of growing conditions, extraction procedures, and environmental variables on the phenolic content of arugula.

The treatments induced a similar trend in total flavonoid content (TFC) and TPC. Specifically, treatments with 0.25 and 1.0 mg L⁻¹ KIN resulted in a slight increase in flavonoid content (Figure 2B), reaching 7.42 ± 0.12 and 7.40 ± 0.04 mg QE g⁻¹ DW compared to the control group (6.43 ± 0.04 mg QE g⁻¹ DW). These results suggest that low concentrations of KIN positively influenced the flavonoid

content. Leafy salads and leaf extracts of arugula have been shown to possess antioxidant [25], and antigenotoxic properties [26], likely due to their antioxidant molecules' content. This indicates that the increased TPC and TFC in treated samples may enhance the plant's biological activities. In a study by Pasini et al. [27], TFC value ranging from 9.99 to 31.39 mg QE g⁻¹ DW was reported from *E. sativa*. Similarly, Mazzucotelli et al., noted a flavonoid content of 17.3 mg g⁻¹ FW in arugula plants grown under natural

conditions [23]. However, Bouacida et al. [21], found lower flavonoid content, ranging from 13.00 to 15.80 mg QE g⁻¹ extract, while Sihem et al. [24] reported an even lower flavonoid content of 2.14 mg QE g⁻¹ extract in methanol extracts of arugula leaves. These previous findings highlight the variability in the synthesis capacity of bioactive compounds in arugula, which may be influenced by differences in growing conditions and extraction methods.

Figure 2. The effects of GA₃ and KIN on total phenolic substance (A) and flavonoid contents (B) of *in vitro* grown *Eruca vesicaria* subsp. *sativa* seedlings.

4. Conclusions

The study concludes that plant growth regulators (GA₃ and KIN) significantly contribute to seed germination and the development of organs, especially at low concentrations. Similarly, these concentrations can increase the synthesis of phenolic and flavonoid compounds in arugula. Also, the findings suggest that KIN can serve as an effective plant growth regulator to improve antioxidant properties in arugula. However, further research is needed to optimize the application and evaluate the efficacy of various concentrations of PGRs in increasing phenolic and flavonoid content.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

5. References

- [1] Elshafie, H. S., Camele, I., & Mohamed, A. A. (2023). A comprehensive review on the biological, agricultural and pharmaceutical properties of secondary metabolites based-plant origin. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(4), 3266.
- [2] Inestroza-Lizardo, C., Silveira, A. C., & Escalona, V. H. 2016. Metabolic activity, microbial growth and sensory quality of arugula leaves (*Eruca vesicaria* Mill.) stored under non-conventional modified atmosphere packaging. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 209, 79-85.
- [3] Espinosa-Leal, C. A., Puente-Garza, C. A., & García-Lara, S. 2018. In vitro plant tissue culture: means for production of biological active compounds. *Planta*, 248, 1-18.
- [4] Mofokeng, M. M., Du Plooy, C. P., Araya, H. T., Amoo, S. O., Mokgehele, S. N., Pofu, K. M., & Mashela, P. W. 2022. Medicinal plant cultivation for sustainable use and commercialisation of high-value crops. *South African Journal of Science*, 118(7-8), 1-7.
- [5] Dias, M. I., Sousa, M. J., Alves, R. C., & Ferreira, I. C. 2016. Exploring plant tissue culture to improve the production of phenolic compounds: A review. *Industrial crops and products*, 82, 9-22.
- [6] Aryal, S., Baniya, M. K., Danekhu, K., Kunwar, P., Gurung, R., & Koirala, N. 2019. Total phenolic content, flavonoid content and antioxidant potential of wild vegetables from Western Nepal. *Plants*, 8(4), 96.
- [7] Murashige, T., & Skoog, F. 1962. A revised medium for rapid growth and bio assays with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiologia plantarum*, 15(3).

- [8] Kıran Acemi, R., Acemi, A., Çakır, M., Polat, E. G., & Özen, F. 2020. Preliminary screening the antioxidant potential of *in vitro*-propagated *Amsonia orientalis*: An example to sustainable use of rare medicinal plants in pharmaceutical studies. Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy, 17, 100302.
- [9] Singleton, V. L., Orthofer, R., & Lamuela-Raventós, R. M. 1999. Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent. In Methods in enzymology (Vol. 299, pp. 152-178). Academic press.
- [10] Dewanto, V., Wu, X., Adom, K. K., & Liu, R. H. 2002. Thermal processing enhances the nutritional value of tomatoes by increasing total antioxidant activity. Journal of agricultural and food chemistry, 50(10), 3010-3014.
- [11] Sudheer, W. N., Praveen, N., Al-Khayri, J. M., & Jain, S. M. 2022. Role of plant tissue culture medium components. In Advances in Plant Tissue Culture (pp. 51-83). Academic Press.
- [12] Cüce, M., & Muslu, A. S. 2022. Sodium nitroprusside mediates attenuation of paraquat-mediated oxidative stress in *Eruca sativa* in vitro. Physiology and Molecular Biology of Plants, 28(1), 289-299.
- [13] Banjac, N., Krstić-Milošević, D., Mijalković, T., Petrović, M., Ćosić, T., Stanišić, M., & Vinterhalter, B. 2023. In vitro shoot multiplication and regeneration of the recalcitrant rocket (*Eruca sativa* Mill.) variety Domaća Rukola. Horticulturae, 9(5), 533.
- [14] Bhagat, S., Rastogi, N. K., Bajeli, J., Tripathi, A., & Tiwari, J. K. 2023. Effect of different seed treatments to promote germination in spine gourd (*Momordica dioica* Roxb.). Plant Physiology Reports, 28(4), 620-626.
- [15] Wang, H., & Shang, Q. 2020. The combined effects of light intensity, temperature, and water potential on wall deposition in regulating hypocotyl elongation of *Brassica rapa*. PeerJ, 8, e9106.
- [16] Beemster, G. T., & Baskin, T. I. 2000. Stunted plant 1 mediates effects of cytokinin, but not of auxin, on cell division and expansion in the root of *Arabidopsis*. Plant Physiology, 124, 1718-1727.
- [17] Li, G., Zhu, C., Gan, L., Ng, D., & Xia, K. 2015. GA₃ enhances root responsiveness to exogenous IAA by modulating auxin transport and signalling in *Arabidopsis*. Plant Cell Reports, 34(3), 483-494.
- [18] Manach, C., Scalbert, A., Morand, C., Rémésy, C., & Jiménez, L. 2004. Polyphenols: food sources and bioavailability. The American journal of clinical nutrition, 79(5), 727-747.
- [19] Donn, P., Barciela, P., Perez-Vazquez, A., Cassani, L., Simal-Gandara, J., & Prieto, M. A. 2023. Bioactive compounds of *Verbascum sinuatum* L.: health benefits and potential as new ingredients for industrial applications. Biomolecules, 13(3), 427.
- [20] Zappia, A., De Bruno, A., Piscopo, A., & Poiana, M. 2019. Physico-chemical and microbiological quality of ready-to-eat rocket (*Eruca vesicaria* (L.) Cav.) treated with organic acids during storage in dark and light conditions. Food science and biotechnology, 28, 965-973.
- [21] Bouacida, S., Snoussi, A., Fauconnier, M. L., & Bouzouita, N. 2016. Glucosinolate profiles by HPLC-DAD, phenolic compositions and antioxidant activity of *Eruca vesicaria longirostris*: Impact of plant part and origin. Mediterranean Journal of Chemistry, 5(5), 528-539.
- [22] Tiveron, A. P., Melo, P. S., Bergamaschi, K. B., Vieira, T. M., Regitano-d'Arce, M. A., & Alencar, S. M. 2012. Antioxidant activity of Brazilian vegetables and its relation with phenolic composition. International journal of molecular sciences, 13(7), 8943-8957.
- [23] Mazzucotelli, C. A., González-Aguilar, G. A., Villegas-Ochoa, M. A., Domínguez-Avila, A. J., Ansorena, M. R., & Di Scala, K. C. 2018. Chemical characterization and functional properties of selected leafy vegetables for innovative mixed salads. Journal of Food Biochemistry, 42(1), e12461.
- [24] Sihem, H., Aicha, M., Radia, C., Nadia, Z., & Katiba, B. 2022. Phytochemical characterization, antioxidant and analgesic potentials of aerial parts of *Eruca vesicaria*. South Asian Journal of Experimental Biology, 12(5).
- [25] Degl'innocenti, E., Pardossi, M., Tattini, and L. Guidi. 2008. Phenolic compounds and antioxidant power in minimally processed salad. J. Food Biochem. 32:642-653.
- [26] Jin, J., O. A. Koroleva, T. Gibson, J. Swanson, J. Magnan, Y. Zhang, I. R. Rowland, and C. Wagstaff. 2009. Analysis of phytochemical composition and chemoprotective capacity of Rocket (*Eruca sativa* and *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*) leafy salad following cultivation in different environments. J. Agric. Food Chem. 57:5227-5234.

- [27] Pasini, F., Verardo, V., Caboni, M. F., & D'Antuono, L. F. 2012. Determination of glucosinolates and phenolic compounds in rocket salad by HPLC-DAD-MS: Evaluation of *Eruca sativa* Mill. and *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* L. genetic resources. Food Chemistry, 133(3), 1025-1033.